

DIVERSITY OF *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA* IN FRANCE

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While listed as a quarantine pest for Europe *Xylella fastidiosa* emerged in France and this is evidenced through the survey of coffee plant trading from Latin America as well as the survey of natural settings. Since the discovery of the first contaminated foci of *Polygala myrtifolia* shrubs showing leaf scorch symptoms in France during 2015 summer, numerous plants have been screened, ending in the identification of more than 300 foci. Here, we report on the diversity of *X. fastidiosa* infections over the year 2015 in France in natural settings and in imported coffee plants. Multilocus sequence typings revealed that several subspecies and sequence types are associated to the emergence of *X. fastidiosa* in France. Evidences of recombination and mixed infections in a same plant have been found. The genomes of some strains of *X. fastidiosa* subsp. *multiplex* that were isolated in France were sequenced and compared to their American relatives. Pathogenicity of these strains is also tested on *P. myrtifolia* and other potential hosts. Altogether, these analyses suggest that *X. fastidiosa* has been introduced several times in France via various plant material from different origins. This work was done as part of INRA's duties in WP2, task 2a and WP3, task 3a of POnTE project.